

TRAIN4EU

Transforming ReseArch & INnovation
agendas and support in 4EU+

H2020-IBA-SwafS-Support-1-2020

Project no.: **101016674**

Start date of project: **1 January 2021**

Duration of project: **36 months**

Deliverable

Reference number and title:

D 8.10 Data Management Plan Second Update

Name of lead beneficiary:

University of Copenhagen

Due date:

30. November 2023

Submission date:

22. November 2023

Dissemination level: Public

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101016674.

Deliverable Overview

Deliverable title: D 8.10 Data Management Plan Second Update

Work Package: WP 8 Management [Month 1-36] led by University of Copenhagen

Deliverable summary: Deliverable 8.10 Data Management Plan Second Update outlines minor updates to TRAIN4EU's initial Data Management Plan (DMP), as described in D 8.8 (M6) and DMP first update D 8.9 (M23). There have been no significant data developments within the project since D 8.9 DMP First Update.

D 8.10 provides minor updates in the following sections, as outlined in D 8.8:

- Section 1 1.4 Data formats
- Section 2 2.2 Making Data Accessible
2.3 Making Data Interoperable
2.4 Making Data Re-Usable
- Section 3 3.2 Costs & Financing

The DMP's main body of text, as contained in D 8.8, will remain unchanged in the second update D 8.10, as D 8.8 continues to be valid in terms of outlining the planned management of data collected, processed and generated in TRAIN4EU work packages (WPs). The aim remains to develop and ensure good management of data during and after TRAIN4EU's lifetime.

D 8.10 only has very minor textual revisions, reflecting the more advanced stage of the project as compared to D 8.9 (M23).

TRAIN4EU'S DMP is in compliance with the ORDP: Open Research Data Pilot requirement for Horizon 2020 funded projects. In line with the ORDP, the DMP follows the principle "as open as possible, as closed as necessary".

Prepared by: D 8.10. is prepared by TRAIN4EU project manager (TRAIN4EU PM) Miriam Kocktvedgaard Zeitzen, University of Copenhagen.

Submission schedule:

Data Management Plan	Version	Date	Prepared By
DMP Initial	1	16. June 2021	TRAIN4EU PM
DMP Initial	final	26. June 2021	TRAIN4EU PM
DMP First Update	final	29. Nov. 2022	TRAIN4EU PM
DMP Second Update	final	22. Nov. 2023	TRAIN4EU PM

Dissemination level: Public - Open Research Data Pilot

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Project Abstract

TRAIN4EU+ is rooted in the 4EU+ alliance’s ambition to strive for excellence in all aspects of our roles as comprehensive, public research-based and excellence focused European universities. Specifically, this proposal will be a transforming effort in our ongoing work to improve and expand how we i) support our researchers as they continue to expand the limits of knowledge and ii) ensure that this knowledge helps society address the challenges of our times, through the pursuit of five objectives:

i) We will find new ways to improve - individually and collectively – our support structures for enhancing quality and impact of R&I; ii) We will foster a culture of co-learning and co-innovation across the consortium based on a thorough best-practice assessment; iii) We will pilot selected transformative measures within different modules within the project life time; iv) We will push boundaries by pinpointing and highlighting drivers and facilitators of, as well as barriers and obstacles, to transformative change, v) We will strive to scale up impact, in collaboration with other alliances, and through dissemination and communication to all stakeholders, including targeted events for policy makers, to ensure wide uptake and exploitation of results.

To pursue these objectives, we rely on a systematic methodology to uncover best practices and lessons learned across R&I support functions, to stakeholder involvement, to share and co-develop innovations and ideas for transformative action across all six universities in 4EU+. We implement this methodology in a concerted effort across our six core work packages that each relate to the relevant transformation modules. An ambitious dissemination and outreach effort will ensure our learnings are made available for policy makers, universities, civil society, business and other stakeholders; thus providing invaluable input to the ongoing effort of preparing European universities for the future.

Topical Work Packages, where data will be collected, processed and generated:

- WP 1 – **Developing Common Research Agenda**, led by University of Milano (UM), Italy
- WP 2 – **Strengthening R&I Human Capital**, led by Charles University (CU), Czech Republic
- WP 3 – **Sharing Research Infrastructure**, led by Heidelberg University (HU), Germany
- WP 4 – **Linking Academia – Business – Citizens**, led by Sorbonne University (SU), France
- WP 5 – **Mainstreaming Open Science**, led by University of Warsaw (UW), Poland

Cross-cutting Work Packages, where data from the topical WPs will be used and managed:

- WP 6 – **Governance for Joint Collaboration**, led by University of Copenhagen (UCPH), Denmark
- WP 7 – **Dissemination, Exploitation, Communication**, led by University of Copenhagen
- WP 8 – **Management**, led by University of Copenhagen

1. Data summary

Activities in the TRAIN4EU WPs were initiated in September 2021 [M9]. As of M35, new and/or unexpected data management restrictions and requirements have not emerged in the WPs. D 8.10 DMP second update will not alter the main body of text of the initial DMP D 8.8, as it continues to support the provision of overall guidelines for data management in TRAIN4EU.

1.1 Data description

Purpose of data collection in relation to project objectives. Data will be collected in TRAIN4EU to complete project tasks and deliverables in order to meet the project objectives as outlined above and in Annex 1 of the Grant Agreement. TRAIN4EU aims to strengthen collaboration between partner universities within R&I domains in focal areas identified in WP 1-5. A key impact will be to raise awareness about opportunities for collaboration among staff members and researchers across 4EU+.

Data utility. To meet project objectives and follow the Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication (DEC) plan, data generated within TRAIN4EU will be useful for internal and external stakeholders, as listed in section 2.2.1 *Stakeholders: users, multipliers and target groups* in Annex 1 of the Grant Agreement. Please see deliverable 7.1 Draft DEC plan for further details.

Internal stakeholders include 4EU+ Governing Board with rectors and vice-rectors, Management Committee; 4eu+ Secretary General and local heads of 4eu+ Alliance offices; 4EU+ flagship programme committees; researchers, scientific bodies and research infrastructure teams; students at all levels including Ph.D., as well as administrative and technical staff from partner universities.

External stakeholders include the European Commission (DG RTD, DG EAC); regional and national policymakers; university organisations such as EUA, LERU, LERU-CE7, IARU etc.; other European universities; national rectors assemblies; associated partners of 4EU+; national and private funding agencies and foundations; business funding agencies and investors; the general public.

Data collected in WP 1-5 will to a large extent remain in raw form as text documents etc. for internal WP use, e.g. as basis for analyses carried out as part of WP tasks. Some raw data, such as in-depth analyses of initiatives undertaken at partner institutions, might be useful to a wider group of internal and external stakeholders, including university leadership when assessing the current state-of-the-art within 4eu+ or planning initiatives related to the R&I focal areas, or state research governing bodies. Final project reports will be uploaded to a data repository for open access, as noted below.

1.2 Data volume

The expected size of data collected and generated within TRAIN4EU is not yet known. Activities in the WPs will be rolled out in September 2021 [M9], making it presently unclear which types and amounts of data will be collected and generated, and deposited for long-term preservation. An estimation of data volume will be included in the DMP first update, due November 2022 [M23].

TRAIN4EU is not a research project. WPs will not engage in research nor will they generate data of exceptional size or complexity requiring specialist hardware or software. Data will almost exclusively be limited digital textual data in standard widely available proprietary file formats such as [Microsoft](#)

Word or Portable Document Format (PDF) in [Adobe Acrobat](#), which all partners have licensed access to, and open formats like OpenDocumentText, compatible with Word and open source applications.

Double digit Gigabyte is a realistic guesstimate of data volume for project data generated as part of collection, analysis, archiving and dissemination. Such data volume is well within locally available storage capacities and technical support, and it will not pose challenges when accessing, sharing or transferring project data. Data volume is not expected to grow into more than one Terabyte in size.

D 8.9 DMP first update

The expected size of data collected and generated within TRAIN4EU's lifetime is presently estimated to be within 5 to 10 Gigabyte in each of the topical WPs 1-5, as well as in the cross-cutting WPs 6-8. Estimates are based on current and planned WP activities, initiated in M9. Data volume is not expected to grow into more than one Terabyte in size in total, as indicated in D 8.8.

1.3 Data collection

Data collection in TRAIN4EU will focus on support functions within research, administrative and technical domains at partner universities. Participants in the WPs are almost exclusively staff at 4EU+ partner universities, who will provide data regarding their professional areas of expertise, or compile or derive data from pre-existing relevant data sourced from their home universities.

Methods for obtaining data in the first six months of the project have included self-administered online worksheets to compile information on existing partner policies, procedures and practices, as textual or tabular data. The data has formed the basis for assessing and analysing WP focus areas and case studies, as part of the protocols to be submitted as deliverables 1.1 – 5.1 on 30. June 2021.

Data collection methodologies will be developed by WP leads as the project unfolds, and needs and requirements become clearer. Data will continue to be primarily collected from partner universities and cooperating institutions and partners. Inclusion of project participants among internal and external stakeholders will be guided by their professional relevance to the specific WP tasks. WP teams will avoid collecting data that are unnecessary, unnecessarily detailed or not significant for WP tasks, in compliance with the 'data minimisation principle' as per [article 5 \(c\)](#) of the GDPR

In TRAIN4EU, data collection will follow methodological tools and ethical guidelines developed for social sciences and humanities research. For data collection from human participants, this includes questionnaires, interviews or focus group discussions. If it becomes necessary to collect, process and store limited personal information about participants, privacy issues will be managed according to appropriate regulations. Participants who choose to participate as identifiable respondents may give consent to the processing of their ordinary personal data, as per [Article 6 \(1\), \(a\)](#) of the GDPR. Please refer to section 5. Ethical aspects below, and deliverable D 9.1, for handling of personal data.

Data origin and re-use. Data collected in WPs will mostly be comprised of re-used, non-confidential data generated by partner universities, such as internal reports, analyses, policies, meetings records, legal documents as well as interviews, workshops and information on partners' websites. Much of the data will already be publicly accessible, such as diversity policies or industrial partnerships.

Content analysis such as SWOT analysis will generate new data, and may expose areas requiring confidentiality. Appropriate measures will be put in place for handling non-public data in WPs.

Data may also be collected from relevant external stakeholders across the partner countries, and potentially other European countries. External stakeholders will mostly come from named publically identifiable institutions and already established partnerships with 4eu+ partners, who will provide data regarding their professional domains of expertise. For data sourced externally, declarations confirming that the data is publicly available and/or can be freely re-used in the project will be provided, along with permissions by owners/managers of the utilised data, if applicable.

Payment for re-use, or restrictions on re-use and sharing of existing third-party data, will be handled by WP leads if and when necessary, including copyright and Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) issues.

1.4 Data formats

Descriptions of data types and formats in TRAIN4EU is work in progress. As the project unfolds, new data types may be collected and generated, requiring other formats. An updated description of data types and formats will be included in the DMP first update, due November 2022 [M23].

Data types. Qualitative data gathered and analysed in a non-numeric form will be the primary data in TRAIN4EU. It will primarily consist of data compiled or derived from pre-existing data, as noted, including text-based documents such as reports, white papers, meeting minutes, records of workshops, interview transcripts, e-mail correspondance etc, as well as spreadsheets with textual or tabular data. Data may also include images, slides, graphics etc. The data will hence be reproducible.

To the extent that human participants will be involved in the project, data collected and generated will also be qualitative data, e.g. interviews with research support specialists at partner institutions. Audio or video recordings of human participants are not expected, but may be included if relevant.

Quantitative data based on numerical or categorical variables, e.g. tabular data such as surveys, might be included in the data collected, e.g. university reports. Preexisting quantitative data will not require validation, quality control etc. Collection of new quantitative data is not expected, but may be included if relevant. New raw data, e.g. obtained from observations, will not be collected.

Data within TRAIN4EU will almost exclusively be digitally based data. WPs are not expected to collect or generate any significant analogue or paper-based data (maps, newspaper clippings, photos, text). Data collected in a physical form will be converted into digital formats for easy access, sharing and secure storage, as well as long-term usability and preservation. For secure storage of physical data, such as informed consent forms (ICFs) signed on paper, see section 4. Data security for details.

Equipment and software needed for digitization is already available at WP home institutions, such as conversion of non-digital data into digital format through document scanner or digital photography. Texts converted through scanners can be saved in searchable and bookmarked PDFs in Adobe. More time consuming methods include entering information manually by keyboard into a text or database template, such as MS Excel, or digitizing text through optical character recognition (OCR) software.

Data formats. The following widely available data formats with application-specific codes are expected to be the primary / exclusive data formats used in TRAIN4EU:

Type of data	Primary formats expected
Textual & tabular data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • MS Word (.doc/.docx); MS Excel (.xls/.xlsx) • MS PowerPoint (.ppt /.pptx) • OpenDocument Text (.odt); Comma Separated Values file (.csv) • Hypertext Mark-up Language (.html) / Rich Text Format (.rtf)
Image data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Adobe Portable Document Format (.pdf) • JPEG (.jpeg, .jpg) / GIF (.gif) / TIFF (.tif, .tiff) / • MOV (.mov)

These file formats will be used because they are:

- community standards for the primarily administrative domains in which TRAIN4EU operates
- widely available open and proprietary formats with partner institutional licensed access
- widely used formats likely to be accessible and usable in the foreseeable future
- formats that support interoperability and re-usability according to the FAIR principles
- formats that have an option for storing embedded metadata according to the FAIR principles

If TRAIN4EU data is to be preserved long-term, assessments of hardware or software environments will be made to ensure continued accessibility, e.g. converting proprietary formats to open digital formats. A resource estimation will be provided in the DMP second update, November 2023 [M35].

D 8.9 DMP first update

Data types and formats in TRAIN4EU remain the same as described in D 8.8.

Data generated so far within WP1-8 are mostly qualitative digitally-based data, primarily text-based documents (deliverables, reports, records of workshops, interview transcripts, meeting minutes, e-mail correspondence etc.). Qualitative data are also collected in the form of presentations (slides, images, tables, figures, graphs, graphics etc.), and of spreadsheets with textual or tabular data, which can include some quantitative analysis of pre-existing open numerical data (e.g., indicators and numerical data from H2020 and HE Dashboards, Scopus etc.).

No special formats, personal data or analog data are expected in TRAIN4EU. The implementation of WP 1-5 pilot actions in the project's second reporting period (M19-36) may potentially generate new qualitative data such as video recordings, pictures and surveys; if relevant, descriptions of any new data types and formats will be provided in D 8.10 DMP second update, November 2023 [M35].

D 8.10 DMP second update

Data types and formats in TRAIN4EU remain the same as described in D 8.8. No special formats, personal data or analog data have been used in TRAIN4EU. Implementation or planning of WP 1-5 pilot actions in the project's second reporting period (M19-36) has not generated any new qualitative data such as video recordings, pictures and surveys, nor any new data types and formats.

In terms of resource estimation, preserving data long-term forms part of planned project procedures as indicated in D 8.8. It has been discussed regularly at TRAIN4EU Steering Committee meetings; please refer to D 8.6 Minutes Steering Committee (M29). Extra staff, software or hardware costs are not expected for long-term data preservation. Please also see section 3.2 Costs & Financing below.

2. FAIR data

FAIR data management. In the first six months of work within WP 1-5 [M 1-6], focus has been on creating protocols on baselining and best practice assessments of R&I support and collaborative frameworks within 4eu+. In this initial phase, WPs have independently implemented naming and versioning strategies for data generated. To make data FAIR and manage data FAIR-ly as the project goes forward, standardized work processes for all data generated will be developed and deployed.

The project manager will coordinate implementation of the DMP plan through various measures to deploy and operationalise FAIR data management throughout the project lifecycle, including:

- establishing the DMP plan as a reflection tool for all project members, serving as a set of guidelines for handling and managing data collaboratively within TRAIN4EU
- encouraging WP leads to share the DMP plan with their entire WP teams, to deploy FAIR data management as part of routine WP data collection and generation practices
- moderating regular team meetings on FAIR data management; meetings at steering committee level with WP leads are planned once yearly, in October 2021, 2022 and 2023.

2.1 Making data Findable

As a collaborative project between six partners leading eight WPs, TRAIN4EU will generate data sets that will be accessed and edited by multiple users in multiple locations. Consistent naming and clear versioning are necessary to facilitate findability of data sets, e.g. keep track of changes and edits to files, synchronize versions across users or locations, and ensure that correct versions are located.

Naming conventions. The WP teams will jointly with the project manager ensure that data sets are clearly named with unique but consistent names across WPs, and clear file structures constructed to help classify, sort, search and discover project files. Basic metadata in terms of information added to files by computers, such as type, date and time of creation and modification, will be supplemented by information in the file name, as the principal identifier of data, to make the data findable.

In TRAIN4EU, the following file naming convention is suggested, consisting of five parts: 1) project acronym TRAIN4EU as prefix; 2) work package number; 3) root composed of short name of object / data set, including WP task number if relevant; 4) version number if relevant; 5) date of last version in YYYYMMDD format as suffix. Each element will be separated by an underscore _. For deliverables, WP number may be substituted by deliverable number, as they contain the WP number in them.

TRAIN4EU_WP no. / Deliverable no._object / task no_version_date (YYYYMMDD)

Clear versioning. Data sets in TRAIN4eu+ will mostly be comprised of text files, and clear versioning is needed to manage different copies or versions of files, files held in different formats or locations, and information cross-referenced between files. WP leads will routinely decide how many versions of a file to keep, which versions to keep and for how long and how to organize versions. Clear versioning will be done by uniquely identifying different versions of files using the systematic naming convention outlined above, which includes version number when relevant and date as suffix, indicating the last uploaded version. Other measures may include creating a file history, version control table or notes included within a file, where versions, dates, authors and details of changes to the file are recorded.

TRAIN4EU's main file sharing platform [MS Teams](#) will be used to store milestone and master versions of files; files for wider circulation with the 4eu+ community can be stored on the [4eu+ Sharepoint](#).

Metadata provision. All data sets generated within the WPs will be provided with metadata to facilitate findability and sharing. Likewise, uniform format or style across WPs for all data files, spreadsheets, interview transcripts, records etc. collected, processed and generated within WPs will also be a priority, as outlined above. All data sets within TRAIN4EU will as part of their metadata contain the following information, in accordance with Grant Agreement Article 29.4:

- the terms ["European Union (EU)" and "Horizon 2020"];
- the name of the action, acronym and grant number;
- the name / title of file and the author, if relevant;
- the publication date, dissemination level and length of embargo period if applicable;
- a persistent identifier.

[Zenodo](#), the anticipated digital repository for TRAIN4EU data, has tools available to assist in creating structured metadata, so non-confidential and non-personal or sensitive data can easily be found and shared via its platform. By providing basic discovery metadata such as titles, authors, subjects and keywords online, more potential new users can find the project data. Basic metadata is generated automatically for files by software programmes such as MS Word, including file format and size, author, date and modifications. This will be supplemented manually by information in the file name.

Rich metadata can be added via documentation providing new users with necessary information to prevent misuse or misinterpretation, as well as to enable the data to be read and interpreted in the future and reproduce the results. This includes describing the context of a specific data element, information on the methodology used to collect the data and the organization of a data collection, analytical and procedural information, and licensing conditions for a data set etc..

Metadata can be placed separately from the data in external files or tables, such as a 'ReadMe' text file that explains the structure of the files with links to each item. Naming conventions for 'ReadMe' files will be developed if and when it becomes relevant. Metadata can also be embedded in the actual file, such as file headers or textual abstract describing the data and including topical keywords such as research and innovation etc. Rich metadata is essential for data deposited in repositories for archiving or preservation and dissemination after the end of the project.

Metadata standards. As TRAIN4EU is not a research project and does not fall in a specific discipline, there are no particular community standards to describe and structure project data. TRAIN4EU metadata will provide bibliographic information like author, date and version number, descriptive keywords and links to related data sets and publications, but not research related information like technical specifications of instruments and software. As disciplinary metadata standards are not available, metadata will have to be created to describe the data and aid discovery through approximation to available metadata specifications, such as the [DublinCore](#) Metadata Initiative.

As the project unfolds, WP teams will have to identify which subject specific standards for metadata to approximate to best ensure data access and re-use. They may have to work with several metadata formats depending on the type of data generated and where the metadata is to be used. Specific metadata provisions, including the use of specific vocabularies such as [ORCID](#) identifiers for people, or whether metadata should be associated with the data set files or be added externally, e.g. when deposited in Zenodo, cannot yet be made, as WP activities will be rolled out in September 2021 [9].

Search keyword. Keywords will form part of the metadata. As the project unfolds, efforts will be made to identify and use relevant vocabulary in descriptive metadata fields to support consistent, accurate, and quick indexing and retrieval of data, and register and/or index data and metadata as a searchable resource. The Dublin Core may be consulted for relevant controlled vocabulary, as noted, including keywords and their synonyms, to be used for indexing and subject headings of data and metadata.

Digital Object Identifier. To facilitate identification, accessibility and dissemination, each data set to be openly shared will be provided with the persistent and unique identifier [DOI](#) or Digital Object Identifier. DOIs will be created through the generalist data repository Zenodo, where data sets are expected to be deposited after project end, as outlined below. All versions of the data set will have the same DOI identifier, but be distinguishable through their version number.

Removing hidden metadata from files. In the event that data needs to be anonymized to protect personal information, files will be checked for hidden metadata that may enable identification. Hidden technical metadata may be saved when files are created or edited, and may include location information and information about a user profile or the owner of the device used to create the data. In TRAIN4EU, much of the data will consist of text files created and directly submitted by internal or external WP participants themselves. Here the risk of identification from metadata is particularly high, as the hidden metadata of these files refer to the participants explicitly. Standard technical metadata can be removed by using common text editors such as MS Office.

Data organization. Last but not least, making data findable requires a clear folder structure for files. Well-ordered data based on logical file names and well-organised folder structures make it easier to find, manage and re-use data files and versions. Naming and structuring of files and folders have so far been implemented independently, as noted. As the project goes forward, WP teams and the project manager will jointly seek to develop suitable procedures for an orderly structuring of data in a common, consistent way within WPs, to ensure quality and consistency across all project data.

2.2 Making data Accessible

Data sharing. Data generated within TRAIN4EU will be made available for re-use to maximise the potential for dissemination, exploitation and communication of project results. Project data will primarily be compiled or derived from pre-existing publicly accessible data, as WP activities to a large extent will rely on re-used, non-confidential data generated by partner universities, such as internal reports and other institutional information. Making project data openly accessible will be based on a thorough consideration of who may be interested in using the data, such as university colleagues and collaborators, or public authorities, as well as what further intended or foreseeable uses the data might have. It is expected that most data generated will be made openly accessible after project end, in line with the ORD principle "*as open as possible, as closed as necessary.*"

Restrictions on data sharing. Certain data sets may not be suitable for sharing, or only for sharing under restrictions, e.g. due to contractual legal obligations, intellectual property rights, consent agreements or ethical concerns. Which restrictions will apply, if any, will become clear as the project unfolds and confidentiality issues and limits on who can use the data, when and for what purpose may arise. An overview of which data sets will be kept closed and only available to project members and relevant university staff will be provided in the DMP second update, due November 2023 [M35]. The overview will include what measures might be taken to minimise such restrictions, including potentially making metadata accessible along with the coordinator's or PM's contact information for queries about access. Please also see section 2.4 Making Data Re-usable below.

Consent for data sharing. All human participants in WP activities, such as persons being interviewed, will routinely sign an ICF before participating in the project. The ICF will also cover their consent for data to be shared. All data containing personal information will be anonymized or pseudonymised before being shared. Generic ICFs have been developed for use in the WPs as part of deliverable 9.1 *POPD Requirement no. 2 Ethics requirements*; please refer to D 9.1 for further details on ICFs and anonymization and pseudonymization measures. Institutional IT experts can be consulted on such issues as controlling access to shared data files, or data encryption before data sharing or transfer.

Data repositories. At project end, all publicly shareable and non-confidential data in TRAIN4EU, along with their associated metadata and documentation, are expected to be deposited in the generalist data repository [Zenodo](https://zenodo.org/), a free and open digital archive built by CERN and OpenAIRE, and recommended and supported by the European Commission. It is a flexible and easy to use platform for making project data accessible, by enabling sharing of data in any size, format and from all fields of research, which in turn enables broad re-use and dissemination activities.

Decisions remain to be made on which data will be kept after the project ends beyond the four years as stipulated in the Model Grant Agreement, which storage volume they will represent, what the requirements will be to prepare the data to particular standards of documentation or format, and how long data will be stored and preserved. Part of the data generated in TRAIN4EU is expected to be time sensitive, and out of date within the four year horizon, reducing the need for mid to long-term preservation. Requirements to deposit project data in national archives are not expected.

A more detailed overview of plans for mid to long-term data preservation, as well as for curation of data after the project ends, will be provided in the DMP second update, due November 2023 [M35].

Making data available. Project data will be generated in widely available standard formats and software, as outlined in the Data summary section above. Based on the anticipated type, size, complexity and sensitivity of project data, it is not expected that particular methods or software tools to access them are needed. To facilitate accessibility, each data set will be provided with the persistent and unique identifier [DOI](#), as noted, with clear versioning of the data sets.

By default, the data access policy will be unrestricted unless otherwise specified. All accessible data sets are expected to be deposited in archives or repositories without an embargo period, based on standard terms: open access to data files and metadata; data files provided over standard protocols such as HTTP; use and re-use of data is permitted; privacy of users is protected.

For accessibility, storage and sharing of internal data sets, secure institutional data servers or repositories will be used, as well as the TRAIN4EU MS Teams channels. During the project lifetime, raw data and data for internal use will be shared with project members and other relevant staff at partner universities via TRAIN4EU's open MS Teams channels. Confidential data and data not for public use will be accessible to project members via encrypted files on closed MS Teams channels. Open data can also be made available via the [4eu+ website](#) or via websites of partner universities.

A data accessibility plan for TRAIN4EU might look as follows:

Action	When	With Whom	Where
Sharing non-sensitive, non-confidential data	During project	TRAIN4EU members	MS Teams
Sharing sensitive / confidential data	During project	TRAIN4EU members	MS Teams with encryption and data processing agreement (DPA)

Archiving non-sensitive / non-confidential data	After project	TRAIN4EU members	Raw data: ERDA* or local servers; Shareable data sets: Zenodo
Archiving sensitive / confidential data	After project	TRAIN4EU members	If relevant, secure access control storage at partner universities
Sharing non-sensitive / non-confidential data	After project	Any interested parties	Open Access via ZENODO
Sharing sensitive / confidential data	After project	Any interested parties	If relevant, restricted access options with informed consent; e.g. access comm. via ZENODO

*ERDA (Electronic Research Data Archive) is UCPH's institutional archive which can also be accessed by non-UCPH project members. Copies of raw data can be moved there after TRAIN4EU ends. See also section 4.1.

Data licensing. Data deposited in Zenodo will be re-usable under the standard usage license [Creative Commons](#) CC-BY, suggested by the European Commission for data generated in projects funded through Horizon2020. CC-BY or “common-use, attribution only” will be used to make data openly accessible by specifying the conditions for re-use of project data. CC-BY allows data sharing through copy and redistribution in any medium or format, adapting the data by altering, splitting, remixing or merging with other data, as well as building on the data for any purpose, including commercially.

D 8.10 DMP second update

No restrictions on data sharing are expected within WP1-WP6, as all deliverables within the topical WPs are publicly accessible and are generally based on publicly accessible information. It is, however, not possible as of M35 (D 8.10 submission) to give a full overview of whether some data sets will be kept closed and only available to project members and relevant university staff. WP leads will assess and make the final decisions on which project data cannot be shared, if any, after submission of the final WP reports (D1.3-D5.3 & D6.2) (M35).

TRAIN4EU plans for mid- to long-term data preservation, as well as for curation of data after project end, center on the generalist data repository [Zenodo](#). As indicated in DMP D8.8, all publicly shareable and non-confidential data in TRAIN4EU, along with their associated metadata and documentation, will be deposited in [Zenodo](#). Focus will be on depositing the public deliverables from WP1-6 (D1.1-D6.2) and making them accessible and usable for the long term. Any further data to be kept from WP1-6 will be preserved locally in accordance with partner universities' policies and guidelines; please refer to section 4 Data Security for further information on local servers and data management etc. Efforts will be made to ensure that preservation and curation plans comply with institutional and national regulations and policies, ethical guidelines, and Horizon2020 funding requirements.

2.3 Making data Interoperable

There is no standard vocabulary for the types and formats of the non-research data expected to be generated within TRAIN4EU. Nor is it relevant to seek inter-disciplinary interoperability, as work in the WPs does not fall within a particular discipline, but rather covers primarily administrative domains. As the project unfolds, efforts will be made to identify and use relevant vocabulary in descriptive metadata fields to support consistent, accurate, and quick indexing and retrieval of relevant data. The Dublin Core Metadata Initiative may be consulted for standards in terms of controlled vocabulary. Keywords and their synonyms will be used for indexing and subject headings of data and metadata.

A README file (.txt or .pdf) will be created to help interpret and re-analyse data correctly by others. A README file will contain the following information: 1) a short description of what data it includes, optionally describing the relationship to the tables, figures, or sections within the accompanying publication; 2) for tabular data: definition of column headings and row labels; data code; 3) data processing steps, if not described in the publication; 4) whom to contact with questions.

Making project data interoperable to facilitate data exchange and re-use can only be addressed on a general level in this initial DMP. An updated description of data types and specifications on data and metadata vocabularies, standards or methodologies in TRAIN4EU to facilitate human or machine interoperability will be included in the DMP second update, due November 2023 [M35].

D 8.10 DMP second update

There are no relevant updates on data types and specifications on data and metadata vocabularies, standards or methodologies to facilitate human or machine interoperability to be outlined in D 8.10.

In the post-project phase, where focus will be on preserving and curating TRAIN4EU data, the DMP will be periodically reviewed and updated if relevant, to comply with changes in data formats, standards and regulations, as well as to ensure continued access and useability of the data.

2.4 Making data Re-Useable

Data licensing to permit re-use will aim for public re-use of project data. Licensing is expected to be the Horizon 2020 recommended Creative Commons Licence CC-BY, which can be set up through Zenodo. This will allow different stakeholders with different interests in TRAIN4EU data to re-use it, as well as allow machine re-use, e.g. data mining, while also protecting the ownership of data sets.

Copyright and Intellectual Property Rights are not expected to be relevant within TRAIN4EU, as no proprietary or patentable data are expected to be gathered or generated. Before use, third-party data will be checked for copyright or license issues, access restrictions or non-disclosure agreements. If external parties hold copyright to data planned for use within TRAIN4EU, copyright clearance will be sought before using the data. Costs might be incurred if extra time is required to seek copyright clearance or if legal advice is required. An overview of copyright or IPR issues, potential costs and financing, will be provided if and when relevant in the DMP first or second update in M23 or M35.

Data will remain re-usable for the lifetime of TRAIN4EU and beyond. All relevant non-confidential data sets generated in the project will be deposited in the repository Zenodo, to be made available for re-use by third parties after project completion in December 2023. Deposited project data sets will be accessible for at least 10 years, the minimum guaranteed storage time for Zenodo. No embargo period for re-usable data is anticipated. Data sets deemed confidential or not relevant for use by third parties or public re-use will not be made available for re-use.

Data quality assurance processes will form part of routine data management by WP leads and the project manager. They will ensure that data are well described in terms of context and methodology of how data were gathered, created and processed. Such processes already form part of the WP task 1 protocols. As the data collected will mostly be compiled or derived from pre-existing data, quality assurance of the data according to the FAIR principles will primarily involve data documentation to support proper data interpretation.

Documentation will be provided on three levels: 1) project-level documentation will explain project objectives, methodology, and tools; 2) file-level documentation will explain how all files that make up a data set relate to one another; 3) item-level documentation will explain the names of the variables and the meanings of those variables.

No inconsistencies or anomalies in the collected data are expected. As no quantitative data are expected to be collected or processed within WPs, a need for data to be cleaned, checked or verified before sharing is not anticipated. Activities such as spell-checking textual information in data will be carried out as part of all data creation steps, from entry and preparation to data analysis.

The following general criteria will be used to ensure data quality:

1. *accuracy* - the collected data will be accurate
2. *relevance* - the collected data will meet the requirements for the intended use
3. *completeness* - the data records will be completed
4. *timeliness* - the collected data will be up to date
5. *consistency* - the data sets will be consistent.

D 8.10 DMP second update

There are no copyright or IPR issues to report in TRAIN4EU.

3. Allocation of resources

3.1 Roles and responsibilities

TRAIN4EU coordinator David Dreyer Lassen, UCPH Vice-Rector Research, and WP 8 Management at UCPH have the overall responsibility for data management in TRAIN4EU. Project manager Miriam Koktvedgaard Zeitzen, UCPH, is responsible for the routine coordination of data management. Coordinator and project manager will ensure that all data collected, processed and generated as part of WP activities are managed according to relevant university, national and European guidelines, including provisions for documentation, storage, security and preservation.

Work within the individual TRAIN4EU WPs is predicated upon participatory co-design and collaborative processes, which will involve extensive handling and sharing of data between participants from the six partner universities in 4eu+. To effectively and safely manage data, as well as the significant data sharing within, between and beyond WPs, each partner is responsible for local data management within the WP activities they lead. The following named persons or categories of persons are responsible for local data management:

- WP1/UM: UM project support officer under the supervision of UM RDM expert and UM DPO
- WP2/CU: [Milan Janíček](#), participant in WP 5, under the supervision of CU DPO.
- WP3/HU: [Anne Jürgens](#), Project Officer at WP3 under the supervision of UH DMO
- WP4/SU: SU R&I Department liaison officer for TRAIN4EU, under the supervision of SU DPO
- WP5/UW: [Zuzanna Wiorogórska](#), University of Warsaw Library, WP5 leadⁱⁱ
- WP 6, WP7 & WP8/UCPH: TRAIN4EU [Project Manager](#) under the supervision of UCPH DPO

As the project unfolds, WP leads may delegate responsibilities to other project participants for specific data management tasks such as metadata production, storing consent forms, data sharing and assigning access to data. Institutional IT services staff may be involved in providing data storage, security and backup services. The project manager will periodically consult with WP leads to jointly review measures, and ensure that roles and responsibilities in data management are co-ordinated and documented across partners. Updates on roles and responsibilities across partners, if any, will be included in the DMP first update, due November 2022 [M23].

D 8.9 DMP first update

The updated list of named persons or categories of persons responsible for local data management in TRAIN4EU at partner universities is as follows:

- *WP1/UM: [UM project support officers \(Elena Del Giorgio and Andrea Galeotti\) under the supervision of UM RDM expert and UM DPO](#)*
- *WP2/CU: [Milan Janíček, participant in WP 5, under the supervision of CU DPO.](#)*
- *WP3/HU: [Anne Jürgens, Project Officer in WP3, under the supervision of UH DMO](#)*
- *WP4/SU: [Cécile Arènes, Research Data Officer, under the supervision of SU DPO](#)*
- *WP5/UW: [Zuzanna Wiorogórska, University of Warsaw Library, WP5 lead](#)ⁱⁱⁱ*
- *WP 6, WP7 & WP8/UCPH: [TRAIN4EU Project Manager](#) under the supervision of UCPH DPO*

3.2 Costs and financing

Activities in the WPs will be rolled out in September 2021 [M9], and precisely which types and amounts of data will be collected, processed and generated in TRAIN4EU, and which types and amounts of data will be deposited for mid to long-term preservation, is presently unclear. An estimation of potential additional costs for management and preservation of data in TRAIN4EU, as well as specific costs for activities such as transcribing qualitative data (e.g. recorded interviews or focus group sessions), translations or guidelines to ensure consistent formatting, will be included in either the DMP first or second updates, due November 2022 [M23] and November 2023 [M35].

In this initial DMP, costing data management and sharing in advance of WP activities starting up, will focus on identifying the infrastructure resources that might be needed to preserve and make data FAIR and shareable beyond WPs. Resources may include staff time, equipment and tools to manage, document, store and provide access to data. It is presently not feasible to price all data-related activities and resources in TRAIN4EU beyond the overview presented in this initial DMP, but timely resource planning for data management and sharing activities will reduce potential future costs.

Software and hardware: No additional costs to procure or use physical or digital resources such as hardware or software are anticipated in TRAIN4EU. The project focuses on research support and mapping and developing sustainable frameworks for R&I collaboration between partner universities. WPs will not engage in research nor will they generate data of exceptional size or complexity requiring specialist hardware or software. Data will almost exclusively be limited digital textual data in standard widely available formats such as Microsoft Word and Excel, and Adobe PDF, as noted.

The resources needed for data processing, sharing and transfer, storage and backup are already available at no extra cost at partner institutions. WP teams have access to sufficient local equipment,

storage and IT services for project needs, and can use institutional licenses for relevant software. Special measures for data transfer and access are not expected to be required beyond MS Teams, TRAIN4EU's main file sharing platform. TRAIN4EU's MS Teams site is administered by CU. It includes closed member-only channels for secure sharing of confidential data and encrypted sensitive data.

Staff time. Staff hours needed to manage data and make them FAIR already form part of planned project procedures. Tasks such as data documentation, organisation and formatting and preparing data for archiving, dissemination and re-use will be a routine part of WP activities during the project lifetime. As standard project procedures, formatting and organizing data will not lead to additional cost. Templates and data entry forms for individual data files (transcripts, spreadsheets, databases) will be developed if relevant. Some extra staff, software or hardware costs might be incurred if data need to be converted to open or other formats with long-term validity for long-term preservation. Estimates of costs and financing will be provided in the DMP first or second update in M23 or M35.

All qualitative textual data such as interview transcripts will be anonymized or pseudonymized by removing identifying information and concealing the identity of human participants before data is processed, stored and shared. To ensure consistency, anonymisation and pseudonymisation will be planned before data collection or transcription/digitization. As data within TRAIN4EU will almost exclusively be non-sensitive or non-complex, removal of identifying information from all files, e.g. editor/author name listed in file properties, is not expected to incur extra costs. For details on anonymisation and pseudonymisation techniques in TRAIN4EU please see deliverable D 9.1.

The need for a dedicated data manager is not expected in view of the non-complex and non-sensitive data anticipated to be generated within TRAIN4EU. The project manager will coordinate data management, and ensure implementation and compliance with data regulations throughout the project lifecycle. All data management activities will be routinely carried out throughout the project. The need for additional specialist expertise or training of existing staff to handle data is not expected in view of the anticipated project data. The expertise, support and training likely to be required for data handling is already available to WP teams at their home institutions.

Data Repositories. When TRAIN4EU ends on 31. December 2023, relevant project data is expected to be deposited in Zenodo. Plans for the mid to long-term storage, preservation and dissemination of data beyond the duration of TRAIN4EU are not yet developed, pending the types and amounts of data collected and generated. There will be no charges as [Zenodo](#) is a free digital data repository.

Ensuring access to data for safe sharing and re-use beyond the project lifetime is in compliance with TRAIN4EU's obligations as a H2020 beneficiary to continue to exploit and disseminate project results for up to four years after project end, as stipulated in articles 28 & 29 of the [Model Grant Agreement](#). It will also ensure that lessons learned through the pilot project are widely accessible.

D 8.10 DMP second update

No additional costs for management and preservation of data in TRAIN4EU, or specific costs for activities such as transcribing qualitative data, translations or guidelines to ensure consistent formatting, have been incurred or are expected for TRAIN4EU data. Likewise, no extra staff, software or hardware costs are expected to be incurred for long-term data preservation, including if data

needs to be converted to open or other formats with long-term validity. As outlined above, data management and preservation form part of planned project procedures to which staff hours have been allocated, requiring no extra funding.

In the post-project phase, efforts will be made to periodically review and if relevant update cost estimates for managing and preserving data in TRAIN4EU, as they may change over time.

4. Data security

Security arrangements in TRAIN4EU will be proportionate to the anticipated non-complex and non-sensitive project data and risks involved, with appropriate measures for personal or sensitive data.

4.1 Data Security Solutions

Data in TRAIN4EU will almost exclusively be in digital form and will be protected by organizational, technical and physical security solutions, in compliance with institutional policies, procedures and guidelines at partner universities. Security risks will be continuously monitored and addressed locally by WP teams, including in terms of their behavior, and centrally by UCPH as project coordinator. The following policies, procedures, human and machine resources provided across partner institutions' physical, personnel and organisational layers will form part of TRAIN4EU's data security solutions:

WP 1 / UM lead: Data collected as part of WP 1 will be stored locally at the UM [DATAVERSE platform](#). Secure data storage will be under the supervision of UM experts in Research Data Management and UM DPO, and in compliance with UM [Personal Data Protection policies](#).

WP 2 / CU lead: Under the provisions of [Article 32](#) and [Article 89](#) of the GDPR, CU has established IT platforms for processing personal data with an appropriate level of information security. Data will be managed via [procedures for data processing](#) and guidelines of the [Data Protection Officer](#) at CU.

WP 3 / HU lead: The data processed through the UHEI network is managed through the University Computing Centre (URZ), where the URZ Data Protection department provides data management and protection. This includes assisting in the development of deletion methods, assessment of and assistance in the development of authorisation concepts, testing the permissibility of data transmission, assisting in the preparation of processing activity directories and contracts for data processing assignments. The IT platforms which process personal data operate under the provision of the State data protection law (LDSG, 12.06.2018), EU General Data Protection Regulation (DSGVO, EU-Verordnung 2016/679) and the Federal Data Protection Act (BDSG, 30.06.2017).

WP 4 / SU lead: All SU collected data is stored according to national safety and security guidelines on IT platforms managed by the SU department for Information Systems. SU has also an appointed Data Protection Officer, [Sylvie Dupuis](#).

WP 5 / UW lead: Data collected under WP 5 will be stored on the server of Univ. of Warsaw Library, IT services department will be responsible for its safety. [National policy](#) and [university regulations](#) will be applied with regard to personal data. As the project unfolds, data will be stored in the open data repository run by UW.

WP 6, WP 7 & WP 8 / UCPH lead : Under the provisions of [Article 32](#) and [Article 89](#) of the GDPR, UCPH has established IT platforms for processing personal data with an appropriate level of security. Data collected and generated within WP 6, 7 and 8 are presently stored on secure university servers. As the project unfolds, data will be stored in the Electronic Research Data Archive [ERDA](#). For storage of personal and sensitive data, [SIF](#) or Sensitive Information Facility will be used. Both facilities are developed for the Faculty of Science, but a general roll-out to all of UCPH is underway.

4.2 Secure storage

Organisational measures relate primarily to protection of the physical environment where data is stored, and documented access control to the data. It includes procedures for retaining physical objects, such as ICFs in paper form. Each WP team will ensure that there is physical access control to data collected, processed and generated within their WP. It includes controlling access to buildings, rooms and cabinets where data, computers, media or hardcopy materials are held, through such measures as physical and key card locks, and staff identity cards as requirements for access.

Secure storage in terms of access control is particularly important for data containing personal or sensitive information, which will be treated with higher levels of security and only be accessible to authorised persons from the WPs. For personal or sensitive data stored in non-digital formats, security measures may involve separating data content, e.g. storing pseudonym codes separately from survey files. The same principles will apply to any personal or sensitive data stored in digital files. Please see D.9.1 for further details on handling of personal and sensitive data in TRAIN4EU.

Technical measures for protecting data include secure data storage and regular backup of project data and metadata during the project lifetime. WP teams will manage local data storage and backup, following local guidelines for securing computer systems and files and the use of infrastructure in terms of secure, institutional servers with automatic backup managed by institutional IT teams.

Technical measures may include multi-factor encryption to control access to files, folders or hard drives containing project data. To reduce risk, data will not be stored on laptops, hard drives or external storage devices without encryption, whenever feasible. Cloud-based storage such as Google Drive, Dropbox, OneDrive or iCloud will be avoided. All data containing personal information will routinely be encrypted before being stored or transmitted. Personal or confidential data will never be stored or sent via email or other file transfer means unless anonymized and encrypted.

Access control to the physical infrastructure provided by partner institutions will be supplemented by digital access control, ensuring that only the right people, or machine processes, can see the right data at the right time. Apart from encryption measures, standard security measures such as locking computer systems with a password, password protection and controlled access to data files can be implemented, e.g. 'no access', 'read only', 'read and write' or 'administrator-only' permission.

Leading up to the roll out of activities in September 2021 [M9], work in the WPs has focused on mapping case studies from the six partners to generate protocols, to be submitted as deliverables 1.1 – 5.1 on 30. June 2021. WP work has produced only non-confidential, non-sensitive information, which has been shared on the TRAIN4EU platform MS Teams. WP leads, in collaboration with CU as administrators of 4eu+ digital platforms, are responsible for handling WP team channels, including access control. Partner staff involved in 4eu+ alliance work may have access to open TRAIN4EU MS Teams channels. Access to closed channels, such as Steering Committee, is exclusively for members.

Transfer of sensitive data. TRAIN4EU will, as noted, not collect personal or sensitive data. If limited personal information about project participants is collected, data security for storage, sharing and transfer of personal and sensitive data will be provided by existing institutional IT services. It might include software or hardware to protect data from unauthorised access, use or disclosure, e.g. when transferred from mobile devices, external sites or home equipment to a central university server. Sensitive data will always be encrypted before transfer, and never be transferred by regular e-mail, cloud sharing tools etc. Signing of non-disclosure agreements may be relevant for confidential data.

Data Erasure and Recovery. Locally, project data will remain on partner institutional servers for a yet to be decided length of time before being erased, in line with local research data management (RDM) policies and guidelines. Compliance with the storage limitation principle indicates that personal data no longer needed to conduct the study will be erased as soon as possible. When project data files are to be destroyed, WP teams will use the infrastructure and guidance provided by their local IT services to erase data in a consistent manner, as simply deleting files and reformatting a hard drive will not prevent the possible recovery of data.

5. Ethical aspects

TRAIN4EU will involve participatory co-design and collaborative processes across the six partner universities in 4EU+, and may include limited collection of data from human participants. TRAIN4EU will comply with the ethical principles for data collection, processing and management in applicable national and EU law, in particular the [General Data Protection Regulation](#) (GDPR). TRAIN4EU will at all times seek to protect the values, rights and interests of all project participants, based on the general principle of maximising benefits and minimising risks and harm to participants.

Data will be collected subject to the free and fully informed consent of participants, and will be processed in anonymised or pseudonymised form whenever possible. Data will only be collected when relevant and limited to what is necessary for the project, in line with the 'data minimisation principle'. If it becomes necessary to collect limited personal data during the project, it will be processed with appropriate safeguards to ensure privacy, fairness, transparency and accountability. For details on informed consent, data minimization as well as anonymisation and pseudonymisation techniques in TRAIN4EU, please see deliverable D 9.1 *POPD Requirement no. 2 Ethics requirements*.

5.1 Procedures for identifying, recruiting and including participants

Project participants will primarily be identified among internal and external stakeholders of the 4eu+ Alliance. Internal stakeholders include 4EU+ university leaders (rectors and vice-rectors); Secretary General and local heads of 4eu+ alliance offices; 4EU+ flagship programme committees; researchers (also in their capacity as teachers), scientific bodies and research infrastructure teams; students at all levels including Ph.D., as well as administrative and technical staff from partner universities.

Relevant external stakeholders include the European Commission (DG RTD, DG EAC); policymakers on national and regional level; university organisations – EUA, LERU, LERU-CE7, IARU etc.; national rectors assemblies; associated partners of the 4EU+ Alliance; national funding agencies and private

research foundations; business funding agencies and investors; and the general public. If participants are identified among groups where particular ethical guidelines are to be followed, such as immigrant or minority communities, those will be provided as and when needed.

Recruitment of project participants will follow ethical guidelines and methodological tools developed for social sciences and humanities research. Participants will only be recruited among pre-identified and known actors, and not through such platforms as the internet/social media. Methodologies will include questionnaires and surveys, focus group discussions, formal and semi-structured interviews. WP teams will ensure that research methodologies and recruitment procedures do not result in discriminatory practices or unfair treatment.

Inclusion of project participants will be guided by their professional relevance to the specific tasks in the WPs. TRAIN4EU will not:

- work with persons unable to give informed consent, such as children or minors, vulnerable individuals or groups, or patients
- involve physical interventions on the study participants or collection of biological samples
- include personal or sensitive topics, which might induce stress, anxiety or humiliation
- involve any psychological, social, legal or economic harm to participants
- involve the use of elements that may cause harm to the environment, to animals or plants
- involve risks to the health and safety of any human participants in the project

Procedures for ensuring informed consent from participants. Please see deliverable D 9.1 for details on ensuring informed consent from human participants in TRAIN4EU.

5.2 Procedures for collecting data

WP teams will not collect any personal or sensitive data when administering questionnaires or conducting surveys, interviews or focus group discussions among TRAIN4EU stakeholders. A majority of respondents will be staff at 4EU+ partner universities, who will provide data regarding their professional area of expertise confidentially and anonymously. External stakeholders will similarly come from named publicly identifiable institutions and partnerships, who will participate as anonymous respondents. If project participants choose to participate in TRAIN4EU activities as identifiable respondents, appropriate measures will be taken to inform them of, and safeguard, their privacy rights in relation to the project and dissemination of project results.

5.3 Procedures for processing data

TRAIN4EU's objectives can be reached by processing anonymised / pseudonymised data. Human participants in the project will only be contacted based on their professional insights as they relate to project objectives. Initial contact information for participants will be public contact information already available as part of their professional, commercial or civic profile. This contact information, along with any other personal data in terms of information relating to an identifiable natural person, will whenever possible be completely anonymised by making the data subject un-identifiable. Please see deliverable D.9.1 for a detailed description of anonymisation / pseudonymisation techniques implemented for data processing activities in TRAIN4EU.

TRAIN4EU focuses on professional collaboration between staff at partner universities working in R&I research, technical and administrative domains and their external collaborators. It does not involve:

- collection, processing or transfer of personal data between partners or collaborators
- further processing of previously collected personal data
- processing of special categories of personal data such as sexual lifestyle or ethnicity
- processing of genetic, biometric or health data
- profiling or systematic monitoring of individuals
- data processing methods that may result in high risk to participants' rights and freedoms

In case of doubt relating to data protection laws, a document detailing technical and organisational measures taken to safeguard the rights of the project participants will be developed in collaboration with UCPH's data protection officer (DPO) under the GDPR, and kept on file. It will address issues such as security measures to prevent unauthorised access to personal data, and measures taken to prevent dissemination of project results (including publication on the internet) that may lead directly or indirectly to a breach of agreed confidentiality and anonymity of project participants.

The DPOs of 4EU+ partner universities will be consulted in case of doubt as to appropriate steps to be taken to comply with personal data protection, and appropriate ethical guidelines in terms of data collection, processing and management. In case any unforeseen major ethic issues arise during the project, such as privacy-related issues, potential misuse of project findings or ethics harms to specific groups, the issues will be discussed at the Steering Committee level. If relevant, an ethics committee opinion from the concerned partner's ethics committee will be sought to ensure full compliance with institutional, national and EU laws and regulations.

6. Other

Data management in each WP will adhere to local institutional and national recommendations and regulations, supplementing compliance with EU regulations:

WP 1 / UM lead: Italy does not have national RDM ad hoc policies. Universities and institutions follow and comply with European policies and guidelines. The University of Milan drafted its [Research Data Management Policy](#) in 2017, which will soon be [updated](#). All data collected and processed by UM will be managed in line with UM policies and guidelines, including the UM [Personal Data Protection policies](#) under the supervision of UM RDM experts and DPO, as well as the [Code of Ethics and for Research Management](#).

WP 2 / CU lead: All data collected and processed by CU will be managed in line with CU policies and guidelines, including the policies of the national [office for personal data protection](#), Act No. 101/2000 Coll. on protection of personal data and on amendments to related acts; and [Rector's directive No. 16/2018](#).

WP 3 / HU lead: All data collected and processed by HU will be managed in line with HU policies and guidelines, including the [Data Protection Declaration](#), as well as the Heidelberg University Data Protection Supervisor and the [Heidelberg University Department for Data Protection](#). In addition, the data will be processed in accordance with the central data protection authority of the State of

Baden-Württemberg Universities ([ZENDAS](#)), the State data protection law (LDSG, 12.06.2018), EU General Data Protection Regulation (DSGVO, EU-Verordnung 2016/679), Federal Data Protection Act (BDSG, 30.06.2017) and the EU Charter of Fundamental Rights (2010/C 83/02).

WP 4 / SU lead: All data collected and processed by SU will be managed in line with SU policies and guidelines. It includes the French Charter for Research Integrity, and the French law “*Informatique et Liberté*” (June 1st 2019) on the *Reglement General pour la Protection des Données* (Data protection act), which implements the EU GDPR regulation on data protection in France.

WP 5 / UW lead: In Poland there are currently no research data management policies and guidelines on a national level. Univ. of Warsaw is in the process of preparing its own policy concerning open data. The most important point of reference are guidelines prepared by the National Science Centre, a state-run research grant institution.

WP 6, WP 7 & WP 8 / UCPH lead: All data collected and processed by UCPH, and by UCPH as coordinator of TRAIN4EU, will be managed in line with UCPH policies and guidelines, including the [Danish Code of Conduct for Research Integrity](#) and [The Danish Data Protection Act 2018](#). It is the current legislation governing the processing of personal data in Denmark, supplementing the GDPR.

References

The main body of text in D 8.10 is transferred unaltered from D 8.8, which was written using the online tool [DMPonline](#).

Additional information was sourced from the [UK Data Archive](#).

Notes

ⁱ Underlined and blue colour text have a hyperlink inserted for easy reference, accessible in digital versions.

ⁱⁱ Zuzanna Wiorogórska was appointed as new WP5 lead by UW in November 2023.

ⁱⁱⁱ Zuzanna Wiorogórska, new WP5 lead as of Nov. 2023, has been added in D8.10 DMP 2nd update

